

An Analysis of the Degree of Small Companies' Dissatisfaction with ISO 9000 Certification

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SUMMARY: The aim of this research is to analyse the dissatisfaction that ISO 9000 has created in small companies. Certification is only a guarantee that the company is using a quality management system according to a list of requisites and procedures. However, the benefits that have been attributed to ISO 9000 have often been overstated, so that companies tend to generate high expectations that are difficult to realize completely. This idea is tested over a sample of 131 small certified companies in Spain. The effect of time on the achievement of advantages and the satisfaction of expectations from ISO 9000 is also tested.

KEY WORDS: ISO 9000 certification, certification benefits, small companies.

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1. Introduction

The interest of the academic world for quality management is the logical consequence of its importance in the business world. Nowadays, concepts such as customer satisfaction, continuous improvement and excellence are common words for managers. In this context, ISO 9000 norms came into being with the aim to standardise quality management systems and simplify the task of supplier selection. The new 2000 version of the norm has introduced several points that bring ISO 9000 more in line with the quality management system known as Total Quality Management (TQM).

ISO 9000 certification is becoming more common every day. This is perhaps because the norm is considered to be a guarantee of quality assurance that is obtained through the accomplishment of a list of actions and procedures (Rayner and Porter, 1991). The number of certified companies is continuously growing, mainly in Europe but also in the USA and Japan. There are several reasons for this, but maybe the most important are two: the external pressures to be certified -mainly from industrial customers- and the belief in the benefits derived from the application of the norm. There are researchers that consider that the expected benefits are in many cases unrealistic and excessive (Casadesús *et al.*, 2000). These excessive expectations are often not fulfilled, thus generating dissatisfaction and a critical view of ISO 9000.

The aim of this paper is to study the dissatisfaction produced by ISO 9000 certification in small companies. This dissatisfaction will be considered as the difference between the expectations that companies had on ISO 9000 certification before certification and the benefits they perceive after certification.

The paper is structured in 6 sections. The origins and evolution of ISO 9000 norms and a literature review on its advantages are developed in section 2. Section 3 starts with an explanation on how dissatisfaction is understood and interpreted in this research to subsequently introduce and argue the hypotheses. The research methodology, results and conclusions are presented in sections 4, 5 and 6, respectively.

2. ISO 9000 certification

The relevance of ISO 9000 norms

In 1995, there were 127,349 ISO 9000 certified organizations in 96 countries and this number grew to 510,616 in 161 countries by the year 2001. With a growth rate of 26%, it is reasonable to think that at the beginning of 2004 approximately 643,000 organisations could have obtained the certification.

The ISO 9000 family of norms was revised in 2000. The three previous norms, ISO 9001, ISO 9002 and ISO 9003 of the 1994 version were integrated into a single norm called ISO 9001:2000. This norm is valid for any kind of organisation and is the only

norm to be certified. Up to the end of 2003 the three previous norms and the new one have coexisted, thus giving time to certified companies to adapt their quality systems to the requisites of the new version. As from 2004, all companies must follow ISO 9001:2000 to obtain the certification (ISO, 2001). This new version of the norm includes a revised title in which the words “quality assurance” have been replaced by “quality management” (<http://www.iso.org>). Moreover, the new norm requires the identification and definition of the organisational processes, which are seen as groups of mutually interrelated activities that transform inputs into outputs (ISO 9000 norm). Processes and sub-processes have to be described in the documents of the quality management system and the quality manual must include a map of processes and their interactions. There was only one reference to “customer satisfaction” in the previous version of the norm and now the whole quality system is oriented to “increase[ing] customer satisfaction” (<http://www.iso.org>). That is to say, the new ISO 9000 norm is much more customer focused. The new version also introduces other important changes such as the greater relevance given to employee training and the need for continuous improvement. Clearly, the new version is inspired by principles much more in line with a TQM policy and practice than the old one was. In any case, since the new version is in its first days of application and there are not enough data on its effects, this research has been done with data on the results of the 1994 version of the norm.

Reasons for pursuing the certification and its advantages

The decision to pursue the certification depends on two types of reasons, called reactive and proactive reasons in this paper (Figure 1). Reactive reasons are those related with two other types of reasons: external incentives and external pressures. Common external

incentives are those given by governments in terms of, for example, free training and financial assistance in obtaining the certification. External pressures have three main origins: (1) regulation and public policies, which, for example, often require certification to apply for government contracts or to do certain activities, (2) financial institutions, which sometimes require the certification before lending money, and (3), customers, mainly industrial customers, who demand the certification when choosing a supplier.

--- FIGURE 1 ---

Proactive reasons are those internal reasons that might stimulate the managers to pursue the ISO 9001 certification even in the absence of reactive reasons. Although the ethical principles prevailing within the company and the way in which managers understand social responsibility might play an important role, the search for the benefits attributed to certification is intuited as the main cause for the voluntary adoption of the ISO 9000 norms. For the purpose of this paper, these benefits have been classified into three groups: organisational and control benefits, productivity and costs benefits, and commercial benefits (Figure 2).

The first group includes those advantages related with a better understanding and control of the processes and with a better integration of human resources in the organisational structure. The second group includes those advantages related with an increase in the efficiency of the organisation, which may let the company to have a strategy of cost leadership. The third group includes the advantages of certification as an

instrument to increase customer satisfaction and as an instrument to improve quality image, which may let the company to follow a strategy of differentiation.

The classification process was divided into 4 stages. In the first stage, a list of benefits and advantages found in the papers cited in Figure 2 was made. In a second stage, the number of benefits and advantages was reduced by integrating those benefits which refer to the same thing with different names, that is, by eliminating overlapping. In the third stage, they were grouped according to the three groups previously described.

Finally, in the fourth stage, the different papers considered were assigned to each group. It is important to bear in mind that these three groups are not independent and that there are important relationships and effects amongst them. For example, a better understanding and control of the processes may help to improve productivity and quality, and better productivity and quality may help to attract more customers.

--- FIGURE 2 ---

The company motivations to pursue the certification are important in explaining the outcomes of such certification (Meegan and Taylor, 1997; Huarng *et al.*, 1999; Hughes *et al.*, 2000). According to these authors, companies that decide to acquire the ISO 9000 certification influenced only by reactive reasons, without any internal conviction of its benefits, achieve fewer benefits than those motivated by proactive reasons. It is worth pointing out that, according to an important number of authors, most of the companies pursue the certification because of reactive reasons (Rayner and Porter, 1991; McTeer and Dale, 1994; Ebrahimpour *et al.*, 1997; Brown *et al.*, 1998; Anderson *et al.*, 1999; Hughes *et al.*, 2000; Martínez Fuentes *et al.*, 2000a; Withers and Ebrahimpour, 2000).

Nonetheless, some authors consider that the main motivation has its roots in proactive reasons, that is, it is internally generated (Ferguson *et al.*, 1999; McAdam and McKeown, 1999; Acharya and Ray, 2000).

3. Small companies' satisfaction with ISO 9000 certification

The effect of ISO 9000 certification on company performance has been widely analysed. These analyses have been done from two points of view: financial performance (Simmons and White, 1999, Singels *et al.*, 2001, Heras *et al.*, 2002) and internal performance (Romano, 2000, Sun, 2000). In relation to its effect on small companies, the number of papers is lower. Ragothaman and Korte (1999), Romano (2000) and Sun and Cheng (2002) found that, in general, small companies obtain more benefits than large companies from ISO 9000 certification. However, Romano (2000) considers that the better outcome could be due to the fact that the previous levels of smaller companies were worse, which gives them better relative increases in results.

The different motivations between small and large companies for obtaining the certification have also been analysed. Street and Fernie (1993), Wenmoth and Dobbin, (1994) and Brown and Van der Wiele (1995) found that small companies receive stronger pressures to obtain the certification. Rayner and Porter (1991), McTeer and Dale (1994), Brown *et al.* (1997) and Gustafsson *et al.* (2001) consider that the most important reason for small companies to pursue certification is pressure from customers. This could end in fewer and lower benefits from certification since, as explained above, benefits tend to be higher when the motivation is proactive. On the contrary, Taylor

(1995) did not find a positive relationship between company size and the motivation to pursue the certification. Otherwise, Bryde and Slocock (1998) found that most of the small companies have more negative opinions on certification.

This paper works under the assumption that the degree of satisfaction with ISO 9000 does not depend only on the benefits derived from it, but also on the expectations generated before the certification. Therefore, a company that achieves more benefits than others might feel less satisfied if its initial expectations were greater than the others' expectations.

ISO 9000 certification is a sign of the company's having introduced a quality management system, but it does not guarantee that the system is working properly and is appropriate for improving the quality of the company's products and services. Except for the commercial benefits, which might be achieved only by obtaining certification, the other benefits listed in Figure 2 depend on the way the company applies ISO 9000 and on its ability to take advantage of the certified quality management system.

However, there are some reasons to think that companies are frequently ignorant of this and tend to overvalue the potential benefits of certification. These reasons are:

- ISO 9000 is good business for consultancy companies and they may be tempted to inflate certification benefits.
- The ISO organisation emphasises the advantages of ISO 9000 and does not warn of the possible problems. It is not explicitly announced that the certification in itself does not guarantee the good working of the quality management system; it merely guarantees its existence.

- Most of the non-scientific and practitioner publications have praised and exaggerated ISO 9000 benefits (Executive Report, 1994; Greiner 1998).

These facts lead the company to attribute a large amount of benefits to ISO 9000 certification, thus giving rise to proactive motivations to pursue such certification. Thus, the adoption of the ISO 9000 norms is to a great extent the consequence of unrealistic expectations that are difficult to fulfil and that generate a certain degree of dissatisfaction.

The difference between previous expectations and subsequent perceived benefits may be even larger in small companies. The certification process implies a proportionally greater investment for small companies (Taylor 1995, Gustafsson 2001) and in many cases there are scarce resources to be taken advantage of from the quality management system once it has been implemented. Tsiotras and Gotzamani (1996) consider inappropriate the implementation of ISO 9000 in small companies owing to the important investments and costs that the ISO 9000 process management system implies. Moreover, the absence of a quality department, the absence of appropriate communications amongst departments and the insufficient investment in training (Nwankwo 2000), and so the lesser employee involvement (Brown *et al* 1998) may be barriers to getting the most out of ISO 9000. The research of Chittenden *et al* (1998) concludes that large companies should not require ISO 9000 of their smaller suppliers if these can demonstrate in other ways that their quality is good enough.

The following hypothesis has been extracted from this reasoning:

Hypothesis 1: ISO 9000 certification does not satisfy the expectations of small companies.

Different factors -size, good internal communication, the existence of an organisational culture of quality, the aversion to change, the existence of a rigid hierarchy and so on- that can affect the outcomes of ISO 9000 have already been analysed (O'Brien 1995; Carlsson and Carlsson 1996; Mallak *et al* 1997; Brown *et al.* 1998; Leung *et. al.*, 1999; Casadesús *et al.*, 2000; Halis and Oztas 2002). However, the role of time from certification in the achievement of benefits has been scarcely studied.

As noted before, the commercial advantages of ISO 9000 can be achieved simply by obtaining the certificate, without actual changes in the quality of the company. This is because the customers tend to believe that ISO 9000 is a guarantee of higher quality or, otherwise, tend to consider that the certified company is at least trying to do something to improve quality. Thus, in many markets, ISO 9000 certification constitutes an element for the discrimination of companies in terms of quality.

However, when every company in a sector has adopted ISO 9000, the certificate ceases to be a differentiating variable and it cannot give any commercial advantage. It is just an inexcusable requirement. Therefore, those companies that were the first to get ISO 9000 certification have probably obtained more and higher commercial benefits because of the higher differentiating power of certification at that time. Moreover, the benefits of early adopters of ISO 9000 may have contributed to generating additional expectations in the followers, thus increasing the degree of dissatisfaction of the more recent adopters. According to this reasoning, the following hypotheses are proposed:

Hypothesis 2: The later the obtaining of certification, the lesser the perceived commercial advantages.

Hypothesis 3: The later the obtaining of certification, the lesser the satisfaction of commercial expectations.

4. Methodology

Data

The target population of the empirical study comprises 275 companies that meet the following requirements: (1) the compliance of their quality management systems with ISO 9000 has been certified by AENOR (Spanish Agency for Standardisation), the Spanish member body of ISO; (2) they appear in the 2000/2001 edition of the Business Directory of Castilla y León¹ (Guía Empresarial de Castilla y León, Edicom Grupo Telecyl); and, (3) they have less than 50 employees. The companies meeting the first requirement in Castilla y León were taken from the database that AENOR publishes in its web page (www.aenor.es). A total of 778 entries were available in February of 2003. Choosing a single auditing body guarantees that all the studied companies were subjected to the same assessment procedures and the same requirement levels. Subsequently, the initial set of companies was screened in order to take only those companies included in the Business Directory of Castilla y León. This procedure was primarily conducted in order to pick the most representative companies in this region,

¹ Castilla and León is one of the 17 Spanish regions. It is located on the Middle West, close to Portugal, and it is one of the more extensive regions of Spain, although one of the less populated as well.

although it was also necessary to get the contact details (phone and address) of each company. Finally, the filter of the number of employees reduced the database to 275 companies.

A postal questionnaire was sent to the general manager of each company. A presentation letter explaining the research objectives and asking for collaboration along with an addressed stamped envelope for the return was attached to each dispatch. Additionally, a phone call had been previously made to each of the 275 companies in order to identify the name of the General Manager, to check his/her contact details and to ask him/her for collaboration. Thus, most of the letters were personalised. Some days after the sending, a follow-up call was made to those companies which had not returned the questionnaire and, in some cases, the questionnaire had to be sent again. Finally, this process gave us a total of 131 valid responses, which constitutes a response rate of 47.64%.

Measures

According to the scheme in Figure 2, a list of 15 benefits attributed to the ISO 9000 certification was built from the literature (see Table 1). The intention was to have the three groups of benefits distinguished in section 2 represented. Each company was asked to score on a six-point Likert scale the importance that each benefit had to in their decision to initiate the certification process. These scorings were then interpreted as measures of the expectations that the company had placed in the ISO 9000 certification, that is, as measures of the benefits that the company expected to achieve from certification.

In another independent question, companies were asked to score the extent to which each of the benefits had been achieved after the awarding of the certification. A six-point Likert scale was also used in this case. These scorings were interpreted as measures of the perceived benefits derived from the certification. For each benefit, the divergence between the scoring denoting previous expectations and the scoring denoting subsequent perceptions was interpreted as a measure of dissatisfaction. Thus, 15 measures of dissatisfaction were built by subtracting perceived results from expectations for each of the considered benefits. Positive figures can then be interpreted as dissatisfaction (expectations were higher than subsequent perceived results) whereas negative figures can be interpreted as satisfaction (expectations were lower than subsequent perceived results). Table 1 includes the descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) for each of the mentioned measures.

To test hypothesis 2, all the items referring to perceived commercial benefits were reduced to a single measure by principal components analysis. This factor explains 65.238% of the variance and is interpreted as a measure of the commercial advantages obtained from certification. As shown in Table 1, factor loadings are all high enough (above 0.7) and reliability (Cronbach's α) is acceptable (Flynn et al., 1990). Likewise, to test hypothesis 3, a measure of commercial dissatisfaction was constructed with principal components analysis from all the dissatisfaction scorings of commercial items. In this case, the resulting factor explains 56.225% of the variance, the factor loadings and the reliability indicator also being satisfactory (see Table 1).

The time from certification was measured by the number of years since the first certification of the company was awarded, irrespective of the ISO 9000 version which was used as reference.

--- TABLE 1 ---

5. Analysis and discussion

Hypothesis 1

Figure 3 graphically represents the means of expectations and perceived results for each benefit. According to the interpretation introduced in the previous section, companies tend to be satisfied in those aspects where the column of perceived results is higher than the column of expectations. On the contrary, they are dissatisfied in those aspects where expectations are higher than perceived results. Thus, satisfaction does not depend on the volume of perceived benefits, but rather on the comparison of those benefits with what the company expected to achieve. A priori, the graphics show that, except for process documentation, coordination with suppliers and auditing costs, companies do not fulfil their expectations. The highest differences are found in commercial benefits, which are in turn what was most expected by the companies before certification.

--- FIGURE 3 ---

In order to give rigour to these observations, the significance of the differences between the expectations and perceived results was subjected to statistical assessment for each benefit. Since many of the variables were not normally distributed, the comparison of expectations and perceived results for each benefit was based on a non-parametric test, the Wilcoxon sign test. Table 2 summarised the statistics. For 10 out of the 15 potential benefits, the mean of perceived results is significantly lower than the mean of expectations. It is therefore interpreted that companies are dissatisfied in these aspects and these items appear labelled as 'dissatisfactory'. Differences are not significant in another three benefits. Thus, expectations tend to be satisfied in these aspects, which have been labelled as 'satisfactory'. Only for process documentation (DOCUM), with a confidence level of 99%, and coordination with suppliers (SUPPL), with a confidence level of 90%, the company overcomes its expectations and is favourably surprised. These cases are labelled in Table 1 as 'very satisfactory'.

In general, the data show that the ISO 9000 certification satisfies the expectations in those questions related to the control and organization of the company, except for those more directly related to human resources, that is, workforce motivation and internal communications. ISO 9000 certification tends to dissatisfy companies with respect to productivity and costs benefits and, specially, to commercial benefits. Although with some nuances, these results support hypothesis 1.

--- TABLE 2 ---

Hypotheses 2 and 3

To test hypotheses 2 and 3, two regression analyses were respectively conducted with the factorial measures of perceived commercial advantage and commercial dissatisfaction built in section 3 as dependent variables. The time from certification was introduced as independent variable. In addition, three control variables that might affect the consequences of certification were also introduced: (1) company size, measured by the number of employees; (2) the time required for certification, measured by a four-point scale (less than 6 months, between 6 months and 1 year, between 1 and 2 years, more than 2 years); and, (3) the integration within a group of companies, measured by a binary variable distinguishing those companies in larger corporations from autonomous ones.

Table 3 shows the correlations between the independent variables. Pearson tests are provided for those pairs of variables that can be interpreted as ordinals. For the relationships in which the binary variable measuring the integration into groups is involved, an ANOVA (Student's *t*) test is given. In general, correlation is low except for the relationship between the time from certification and the integration in groups. This result might be a consequence of the exchange of knowledge and the learning economies occurring among companies of the same corporation. The certification of a company in the group is enough to make the initiation of the certification process simpler and more attractive for the others.

--- TABLE 3 ---

To avoid the negative effects of collinearity, two different models were estimated separately. The first one included only the control variables and the second one incorporated the variable measuring the age of certification as well. Table 4 shows the results of this procedure.

According to the low explanatory power (R^2) and the non-significance of any of the control variables, the global fit of model 1 for both dependent variables is not statistically significant. When the time from certification is introduced in model 2, the global fit becomes significant with a confidence level of 90%. Although the predictive power of the model is still very low, the variable introduced turns out to be highly significant. Thus, the time from certification appears as a variable that explains the perceived advantages as well as the dissatisfaction, although its explanatory power is rather limited. This seems quite reasonable if we take into account that, according to the literature, many other factors might affect the success of certification and therefore explain the remaining variance.

The sign of the coefficients of the variable time from certification in model 2 meets the relationships suggested by hypotheses 2 and 3. The longer the time from certification in a company, the higher the perceived commercial advantages and the lower the commercial dissatisfaction derived from such certification. The data therefore support both hypotheses.

--- TABLE 4 ---

6. Conclusions

A model to measure perceived advantages and dissatisfaction derived from ISO 9000 certification in small companies has been developed and applied in this paper. A compilation of potential benefits and motivations was built from the literature on ISO 9000. For each of them, dissatisfaction has been measured by comparing expectations before certification to perceived results after certification.

The growing popularity of ISO 9000 certification has made many business managers think of it as a direct and finite way to success and not as a starting point for developing a serious and ongoing quality management program. The overvaluation and exaggeration of the possibilities of certification and the consequent formation of unrealistic expectations give rise to the dissatisfaction of managers when the results do not measure up to their plans. This dissatisfaction might be even higher for small companies given that they find more barriers to achieve and exploit certification. In this respect, this research has empirically shown that the outcomes of ISO 9000 certification do not live up to the expectations of small companies in many different aspects of business.

The higher expectations of small companies with respect to ISO 9000 certifications refer to commercial aspects: access to new markets, increase of market share and business portfolio, image improvement, and so on. However, many of these objectives

depend on the differentiating power of certification. Such power was significant when ISO 9000 certification was not widely extended and the certified companies stood out from the others. However, insofar as the number of certified companies has grown, the differentiating power of certification has fallen. Empirical data has shown that this effect results in lower commercial advantages and higher dissatisfaction of small business managers with respect to ISO 9000 certification. This result leads us to think that, in the near future, the benefits of ISO 9000 will only depend on the good use of the quality management system that has been implemented to obtain the certification rather than on the mere certification as a signal to markets. Once certification becomes only a requisite to enter some markets, the degree of satisfaction will depend solely on the way in which such certification is achieved. In this sense, an interpretation of the ISO 9000 standard according to the TQM principles and approaches can be a good way to achieve high returns from certification investments.

However, this paper is not exempt from limitations, which in turn can be considered as challenges for future research. Firstly, the target population of the study sample comprises companies within one Spanish region only. Cultural and socioeconomic differences between regions and nations might affect expectations as well as perceived results. Thus, the replication of the study in other regions would, for example, permit assessment of certain geographical influences. Secondly, apart from the age of certification, additional variables should be studied to explain the perceived benefits as well as the degree of satisfaction/dissatisfaction. Thirdly, it would be interesting to consider data from companies certified by other accredited certification bodies in order to assess the effect of existing differences in the exigency levels of the auditing processes.

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